

1 **NK cells from humans with chronic HIV-1 infection.**

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5 We measured total transcription in purified sorted CD3-CD56+ natural killer (NK) cells from humans with
6 chronic HIV-1 infection to describe killer cell biology during a chronic lentiviral infection. NK cells from
7 individuals with chronic HIV-1 infection produced excess interferon gamma (*Ifnγ*) upregulated select
interferon stimulated genes including *Irf27* and *Mx1*. Cells displayed an altered cycling phenotype marked
8 by induction of *Mki67* despite activation of *Cdkn2a*. NK cells were enriched for *Gpr171* in chronic infection
and activated *Irf9*. The *Scimp* gene was silenced on the NK cell during HIV-1 infection.

9 Citations

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